

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ENSURING TRAIN SAFETY

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Abstract. This work is devoted to the automation of accounting for monthly commercial inspections and control over troubleshooting in railway transport. The main problems related to periodic inspections and monitoring of the technical condition of trains and inventory management are considered. It describes in detail the development of an information system and software algorithms, which makes it possible to simplify and speed up the process of accounting and monitoring the technical condition of trains. It provides collection and processing of data related to inspections and repairs, as well as automatic generation of reports and notification of the need for repairs. The principles of operation are given, the goals of creating systems are defined, the scheme of user interaction with the AC of the CMOS is considered. The data analysis carried out by the AC CMO makes it possible to improve the quality of monthly inspections, the level of control and responsibility of managers.

As a result of the work, positive results were obtained and the efficiency of accounting and control over troubleshooting in railway transport was improved.

Keywords: bulk cargo, ITARUS-PBX system, train traffic, auto-locking system, software algorithms, AC of the CMOS

Railway transport has been and remains the leading link in the integrated transport system of Uzbekistan. In the long term, rail transportation will remain the most cost-effective way of transporting significant volumes of stable bulk cargo flows delivered over medium and long distances.

An important direction of improving the work of railway transport in almost all developed foreign countries is the development of scientifically sound management methods that reflect the specifics of the functioning of both individual railway companies and the country's railway network as a whole.

For the first time, the European Standard (EU) for traffic safety management has been introduced on Russian railways. This system is built on the basis of the traditional Russian system and the ITARUS-PBX system modified together with the Italian company. Among its features is the ability to track everything that happens in the transport system in real time, for example, the actual position of trains with an accuracy of 10 meters and their speed, and transmit control commands to locomotives using a special radio channel.

Within the framework of ensuring complete safety of train traffic, a receiver of signals of automatic locomotive signaling of a new generation is being developed, implemented on a promising microelement and nanoelement base using correlation algorithms for receiving and processing signals. At the same time, it is planned to introduce an auto-locking system with tonal rail circuits, centralized equipment placement and duplicate information transmission channels (ABTC-M). This solution is a microprocessor system for interval regulation and ensuring the safety of train traffic on the stages. This system allows you to increase the reliability of auto-locking devices, reduce operating costs, as well as troubleshooting time. A feature of the operation of the ABTC devices is the presence of a circuit for closing and opening the distillation devices, which excludes the appearance of a permissive indication at the traffic light in case of false freedom of the rail circuit.

In the future, Russia wants to improve transport safety through the introduction of innovations such as:

- implementation of systems to ensure the operation of stations on single-track lines
- development of a system of coordinate control and regulation of train traffic based on a digital radio channel

- development of satellite navigation for high-speed and low-activity areas
- development of control systems for train and shunting work at stations based on satellite determination of the coordinates of mobile units and the use of a broadband digital radio channel with a reduction of floor equipment.

But we have achieved safety during movement mainly due to full control of railway territories when installing and equipping video surveillance systems with control in specially equipped points. In addition, special stereo video cameras are installed on the tracks of the station, capable of distinguishing the presence of a foreign object or a working person on the tracks and, if necessary, give the command to stop the train in automatic mode. Some time ago, cameras capable of distinguishing objects and people who do not move for a long time also began to be installed at stations, which also increases the level of security. In the buildings of railway stations and stations where people are located, gas analyzers are also installed, allowing to determine the presence of dangerous substances in the air in time. In the future, they will be installed everywhere.

Currently, the CTCS system of levels 2 and 3 is used on high-speed lines. The further development of China's railway signalling system over the next few years will focus on intellectualization, integration, standardization and openness. Its goal is to reduce costs through the use of technologies that simplify the system while increasing the level of security. This will contribute to the growth of capacity and passenger satisfaction with guaranteed safety and reliability of the high-speed network, which will ultimately make the trip safe, efficient and not have a negative impact on the environment.

There were about 30 NATs in the European Union (EU). railway alarm systems. To overcome technical problems at the borders of such systems, the standard of management, command, signaling, communication – ERTMS was developed, establishing a compatible railway structure throughout the EU. Installed both on the track and on board, it consists of the European Train Control System (ETCS), which ensures that the train does not exceed a safe speed and distance from other trains, and the global Railway Mobile Communication

System (GSM-R), which represents the radio communication standard for rail transport. The ETCS layer defines the equipped path and the way information is transmitted between the path and the vehicle:

- Level 0: Existing outdoor SCB devices are not included in ETCS. the driver visually monitors the signals The on-board system only monitors compliance with the speed limit for this type of vehicle. the composition of the tracked section. This level of implementation is not applicable on international routes, because due to the fact that the visible signals in different countries differ, a change of locomotive crews is mandatory when passing the border.

- Level 1: Information is transmitted via eurobalises or Euroloop (radiating cable), traffic light readings and track data are transmitted to the train. All information is encoded by the wayside electronic unit and then goes to the balises. A special reader under the bottom of the train receives it, the on-board computer decrypts the received data, calculates the optimal speed, braking curve and outputs all the information to the driver's console. The information is updated with each subsequent passage of the baliza. To control the passage of the block section border by train in full, that is, the actual release of the block section, wheelset counting devices are used.

- Level 2: Information is transmitted via GSM-R. The on-board system constantly determines the location of the train based on the last coordinates received from the baliza and the path traveled after that, calculated by the odometer. In the radio blocking center, the received data is compared with the planned train schedule. The results of the comparison over the digital radio network are transmitted to the on-board information and control system of the rolling stock to inform the driver about deviations from the traffic schedule for subsequent decision-making. This allows you to completely remove the floor traffic lights, but the control of the passage of the train in full, as well as on the first level, is carried out by floor devices of the SCB.

- Level 3: Information is transmitted via GSM-R. The vehicle automatically reports its location, direction of movement and integrity to the control center and

receives traffic permits. This allows you to completely remove the signal part on the side of the tracks.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of elements of on-board equipment of rolling stock equipped with ETCS

ERTMS makes it possible to achieve not only safe train traffic, but also the most efficient use of the railway infrastructure, which inevitably leads to positive economic results. The modern approach to ensuring traffic safety on the railways of developed countries is to use a systematic approach in which technology plays an important, but not the only role. In conditions of resource scarcity, it is more preferable to invest in systemic measures that contribute to achieving a high level of manageability of security-related processes. Life safety in railway transport is a set of organizational and technical measures aimed at reducing the likelihood of threats to the life and health of passengers, the safety of transported goods, the safety of infrastructure facilities and rolling stock of railway transport, environmental safety of the environment. It is for this reason that it is necessary to improve safety and introduce modern technologies and artificial intelligence to ensure traffic safety on railway transport.

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